

Visualizing hidden communities of interest: A preliminary analysis of topic-based social networks in astrobiology

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Abstract

Author networks in science often rely on citation analyses. In such cases, as in others, network interpretation usually depends on supplementary data, notably about authors' research domains when disciplinary interpretations are sought. More general social networks also face similar interpretation challenges as to the semantic content specificities of their members. In this research-in-progress, we propose to infer author networks not from citation analyses but from a topic-model of published works. Such author networks reveal, as we call them, "hidden communities of interest" (HCoI's) whose semantic content can easily be interpreted by means of their associated topics in the model. We use an astrobiology corpus of full-text articles ($N=3,698$) to illustrate the approach. Having conducted an LDA topic-model on all publications, we identify the underlying communities of authors by measuring author correlations in terms of topic distributions. Adding publication dates makes it possible to examine HCoI evolution over time, thereby providing a diachronic perspective on the emergence of this recent domain of scientific investigation over the past five decades.

Introduction

Social network analysis is known to provide a wealth of insights about its members and their most significant relationships, but also about network structures and their evolution over time. When applied to networks of scientists, social network analyses can be used in a variety of contexts, for instance to uncover latent social structures or "hidden colleges" (Crane, 1969), or to examine the dynamics of science, including the role of networks and institutions over such issues as problem selection, discovery, or collaboration (Fortunato et al., 2018). Social network analysis presupposes access to data about network members and their relationships. In science, a major source is citation data, which have been shown to provide insightful perspectives onto the structure of scientific social networks (Boyack et al., 2005). Yet, interpreting such social networks usually requires supplementary information, for instance about author research domains or disciplines, which can be obtained by examining key publications or metadata (e.g., keywords) from other sources. To address this type of issue, some have developed topic models that could incorporate relational data between authors (Steyvers et al., 2004), notably in the case of social media and directional networks (McCallum et al., 2007), or in the case of co-authorship data (Zhang et al., 2007). On the other hand, others have proposed to include prior constraining data on nodes so as to improve network community detection algorithms, as done in semi-supervised community detection algorithms and graph neural network approaches (Ye et al., 2018). Here, we propose to construct author networks directly from topics inferred from a preliminary topic-modelling stage. More specifically, the proposed approach starts by fitting a topic-model to a corpus of scientific publications. This stage leads to topic distributions for all publications. These topic distributions can then be averaged out per author, resulting in author topic profiles. Author correlations in terms of topic profiles can in turn be calculated and used to construct author correlation networks. Such networks thereby capture shared research interests among scientists, revealing what can be called "hidden communities of interest"

(HCoI's), that is to say groups of agents sharing similar semantic contents but whose social relationships with one another may be unknown or underlying. As a case study, we use here a corpus of astrobiology articles ($N_{\text{articles}} = 3,698$; $N_{\text{authors}} = 7,838$). Astrobiology can be defined as a domain of research that “embraces the search for potentially inhabited planets beyond our Solar System, the exploration of Mars and the outer planets, laboratory and field investigations of the origins and early evolution of life, and studies of the potential of life to adapt to future challenges, both on Earth and in space” (Marais et al., 2003), or more succinctly as “the study of the origin, evolution, and distribution of life in the context of cosmic evolution; this includes habitability in the Solar System and beyond” (Horneck et al., 2016). The present research-in-progress aims at better understanding this domain of research by visualizing its underlying author networks as inferred from similarities of publication topic profiles.

Methods

For this study, we assembled a corpus including all full-text articles from the three major astrobiology journals: *Astrobiology* (2000-2020), the *International Journal of Astrobiology* (2001-2020), and *Origins of Life and Evolution of Biospheres* (1968-2020). Removing editorials, conference abstracts, errata, and short articles (<4,000 characters) led to a corpus of 3,698 full-text articles with publication dates running from 1968 up to 2020. The corpus was cleaned and pre-processed in a standard way. Only nouns, verbs, modals, adjectives, adverbs, proper nouns, and foreign words were kept, following part-of-speech (POS) tagging and lemmatization (TreeTagger package (Schmid, 1994)); stopwords, words with less than 3 characters or occurring in fewer than 20 sentences in the corpus were removed.

Topic-modelling was carried out with the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) algorithm, following (Blei et al., 2003), with a number of topics K chosen at 25 after manual inspection of several models different K values (hyperparameters alpha and eta were respectively set to 0.02 and 0.01). The model thereby resulted in 25 probability distributions over the corpus terms (each probability distribution representing a topic), and 3,698 probability distributions of these topics over the corpus articles. For each topic, top-words were inspected as well as selected texts, making it possible to interpret each topic and give it a label. Topic-to-topic correlations in documents were also calculated. A topic correlation network was built with Gephi; Louvain community detection (with default parameters) led to 4 clusters with 5 to 7 topics each.

For all articles, author metadata were manually checked (to avoid duplicates due to minor spelling differences). All authors ($N = 7,838$) were assigned publication weights based on the sum of their contributions to published articles (co-authored articles were evenly split between co-authors). The article corpus was then split into five main time-periods of about a decade each depending on publication dates. For each one of these periods, article topic distributions were then averaged per author, resulting in topic profiles for each author (that is to say, author-specific probability distributions over the 25 topics). Pearson correlations between author topic profiles were calculated, leading to correlation networks (built with Gephi). To reduce noise, only authors with weighted publication above 1 were retained (thereby filtering out “transient authors”), and correlation thresholds were set above 0.3. Author nodes were then coloured depending on the dominant topic of their profile. This made it possible to visualize the different communities of astrobiologists and their main research themes depending on time-period.

Results

We share here the preliminary results of this research-in-progress: first, results from the topic-model itself; second, results from the author network analyses at two different time-periods: the

1970s, which offer a glimpse onto the emergence of astrobiology, and the 2010s which provide a more recent window on this domain of research.

Topic-model of astrobiology publications

The results of the topic-model give an overview of the main research topics in astrobiology, as present throughout the publications of the three major journals in the field. These topics can be analyzed by examining their top-words (as in Table 1) as well as sample texts.

Table 1. Topics and their top-10 words. Arranged by topic cluster following Louvain community detection on the graph of topic-to-topic correlations in articles

<i>Topic name</i>	<i>Top-10 words</i>
A - Bacteria-microbes	cell; sample; bacterium; microbial; growth; culture; strain; study; isolate; medium
A - Cell-plant-animal	cell; plant; control; animal; study; change; experiment; increase; effect; level
A - Life-civilization	life; civilization; universe; time; year; earth; make; human; evolution; question
A - Radiation-spore	radiation; spore; sample; cell; space; exposure; experiment; dose; condition; expose
A - Sample-mission	sample; mission; surface; mars; instrument; rover; material; system; drill; test
A - Science-mission	science; mission; scientific; research; field; student; astrobiology; study; datum; provide
B - Amino-acid	acid; amino; peptide; glycine; code; codon; gly; protein; alanine; ala
B - Chemistry	reaction; product; formation; yield; form; synthesis; solution; phosphate; prebiotic; hydrolysis
B - Life-system	system; life; process; molecule; chemical; evolution; energy; form; reaction; cell
B - Organic-molecule	organic; molecule; compound; carbon; gas; form; meteorite; reaction; formation; chemical
B - Protein-gene-RNA	protein; sequence; gene; ma; dna; enzyme; structure; group; organism; genetic
B - Sample-chemistry	sample; experiment; acid; solution; temperature; organic; water; compound; result; analysis
B - Surface-mineral-vesicle	surface; adsorption; mineral; molecule; clay; acid; concentration; membrane; vesicle; water
C - Atmosphere	atmosphere; surface; atmospheric; earth; model; flux; temperature; high; water; cloud
C - Chirality	chiral; molecule; crystal; chirality; enantiomeric; racemic; solution; asymmetric; excess; reaction
C - Impact-particle	impact; particle; earth; event; solar; energy; large; dust; time; mass
C - Planet-star	planet; star; system; mass; orbit; planetary; stellar; habitable; solar; earth
C - Value-model	value; model; time; rate; result; number; give; show; equation; case
D - Life-environment	life; earth; environment; organism; biological; example; condition; early; terrestrial; evidence
D - Mars	mars; martian; water; soil; surface; lake; region; site; crater; subsurface
D - Reaction-vents	reaction; hydrothermal; energy; concentration; iron; carbon; system; oxidation; reduce; hydrogen
D - Rock-sample	rock; mineral; sample; alteration; hydrothermal; carbonate; iron; volcanic; composition; sediment
D - Spectra	spectra; band; spectral; spectrum; feature; raman; wavelength; show; absorption; sample
D - Structure-geology	structure; form; mat; formation; chert; microbial; fossil; filament; layer; surface
D - Water	temperature; water; ice; surface; ocean; heat; liquid; europa; pressure; thermal

The first cluster (A) includes topics that generally relate to living organisms and their survival: research about microbial communities, typically in extreme environments; space biology research; historical-philosophical studies of astrobiology; microbial survival in space; microbial contamination of spacecrafts and landing sites; as well as mission planning. The second cluster (B) gathers chemistry- and origins-of-life related topics: research on amino- and nucleic-acids, on the origin of the genetic code; the prebiotic synthesis of these compounds; definition of life, protocell and artificial life; research in prebiotic chemistry generally speaking; early molecular evolution and early phylogenetics; analyses of chemical samples, notably meteorites; the role of minerals and surfaces in chemical evolution. The third cluster (C) gathers topics that relate more specifically to the “astro” part of astrobiology: research on planetary atmospheres; the origin and amplification of chirality; delivery of matter and energy from space; the dynamics of planetary systems, notably exoplanets; as well as the role played by modeling and data in diverse aspects of astrobiology. Finally, the fourth cluster (D) tends to concern geological and other potential traces or biosignatures of life: habitability and biosignatures; research on Mars; hydrothermal vents; geology; exoplanet spectroscopy; biopaleontology; as well as the search for water on other worlds.

Topic-based author communities

Over the past fifty years, astrobiology has significantly grown in terms both of research domains and authors. We present here our preliminary results on the first and last decades of the corpus, to visualize the changes the discipline has undergone as it emerged and consolidated over the years. In the networks, author nodes have been colored based on their dominant topic; identifiable author communities have been numbered based on topic cluster, with a numerical index when several sub-communities exhibited topics from the same cluster (for instance: d1 and d2 in Fig.1). As can be seen in Fig. 1, the field comprised a handful of communities in the 1970s. A first community (a) focused on space biology research, notably the effects of space-mission factors (e.g., acceleration, microgravity) onto health and physiological functions in humans or animal models (with such researchers as Siegel, Busby or Douglas). A second community (b), and by far the largest, included researchers on prebiotic chemistry and origin-of-life related topics. One notices the dominant presence of Ponnampertuma and his work on chemical evolution, together with other specialists on prebiotic and abiotic chemistry (Klein, Oró). Still in the same community, other researchers focused more on metabolism and chemical transformations of macromolecules such as amino- and nucleic-acids (e.g., Buvet, Hartman). One cannot help to also notice the presence of Alexander Oparin (upper part of the community), the famous Russian chemist who formulated the soup-hypothesis of the origin of life, and of Carl Sagan (lower part). A third community (c) gathers researchers interested in interaction between space and Earth life, for instance via models for estimating terrestrial microbes on the moon or mars (Trauth, Cornell), or on the origin of chirality (Keszthelyi, Thiemann). Finally, two distinct sub-communities appear to tackle different aspects related to traces of life: the first sub-community (d1) gathers researchers mostly interested in the origin of photosynthesis and its traces (Broda, Krasnovsky), while the second (d2) clearly includes micropaleontologists (Schopf, Muir, Knoll).

Figure 1. Astrobiology author network 1968-1979.

Forty years later, the landscape of astrobiologists and their research has considerably enriched (Fig. 2). This shows both in the number of authors and in the number of distinct communities. Two distinct communities gather researchers with topics of cluster A (in red). The first community (a1) includes researchers interested in “big philosophical questions”, for instance about extraterrestrial life and astroethics (Forgan, Crawford, Chon-Torres). The second community (a2) is more focused on microbial survival in space, notably due to radiation or in simulated conditions (Rettberg, de Vera, Schuerger, Billi). Topics of cluster B are now split

between three communities. The larger one (b1) concerns researchers interested in the synthesis of proto-living systems and/or some of their constituents (Benner, Deamer, Luisi). The second community (b2) includes researchers focusing on catalysis and the role of mineral surfaces (Zaia, Kamaluddin). As for the third community (b3), it focuses more on the detection of organics and possible biomarkers (Sephton). Topics of cluster C tend to appear together, though two communities of authors are somehow discernible: community (c1) includes researchers whose work tends to concern the atmospheres and biosignatures of exoplanets (Meadows, Stevenson), while community (c2) concerns more generally planetary dynamics (Barnes, Heller, Loeb). Finally, topics of cluster D are found in two communities, including one which is quite stretched (d1), in between (a1) and (a2): this community focuses on habitability and life in extreme environments (Cockell, McKay, Schulze-Makuch). As for the second community (d2), it includes researchers focusing on geological traces of life, microfossils and other biosignatures (Parnell, Westall, Edwards, McMahon).

Figure 2. Astrobiology author network 2010-2020.

Discussion

The methods we followed make it possible to visualize hidden communities of interest among researchers by analyzing similarities between their respective publication topic profiles. Such communities of interest denote groups of scientists—here, astrobiologists—who share similar research interests. Splitting the corpus by time-periods also provides a diachronic perspective of the evolution of these communities over time, showing a diversification of astrobiology authors as they increase in number and explore connected domains of research. An advantage of the methods over classical citation-based analyses is an improved interpretation of

community research specialties, directly grounded into publication semantic content. Note that the methods can also be used in contexts where no bibliometric data are available.

Work-in-progress concerns the networks for the other time-periods of the corpus. We also plan to use community detection (i.e., Louvain method) in the graph of author correlations to identify author communities. The topic profile of these communities could then be computed by averaging out the topic profiles of their authors. This should give a more accurate and detailed depiction of author communities (revealing community topic profiles) compared to the current dominant-topic approach (limited to a single topic). Also, from a diachronic perspective, the evolution of communities could be studied by measuring the pair-wise distance of community topic profiles from one period to communities of the next period. This would make it possible to identify genealogical links between communities of researchers (and possibly identify bifurcations and mergings) over time.

Conclusion

The present research-in-progress proposed an approach to investigate latent scientific social networks and their evolution through time. In the case of astrobiology, the approach showed a diversification of the research communities over time, and a consolidation as the number of researchers increased. Directions for future research were highlighted.

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